

Regular SPA Resistant Fixed-base Comb Method for Elliptic Curve Scalar Multiplication

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Abstract—Side Channel Attack(SCA) allow an adversary to reveal partial information or exact value of the secret key in a cryptographic device by observing side channel information such as the computing times or the power consumptions. Two main kinds of SCA attacks are Simple Power Analysis(SPA) and Differential Power Analysis(DPA) attacks. In elliptic curve cryptography a particular target of SCA attacks is the secret scalar k in scalar multiplication algorithm. In this paper, we prove that the length of the recoding of the odd scalar k using Joye and Tunstall regular signed-digit recoding with $m = 2$ is equal to the length of the binary representation of the scalar k . Then, we propose a regular SPA resistant elliptic curve scalar multiplication algorithm using the fixed base comb method. Our proposed method represents the odd scalar k in base 2 using Joye and Tunstall regular signed-digit recoding. Then, the scalar k is divided into $\omega \times d$ blocks according to the method of Lim and Lee and processes columnwise. All the columns are non-zero, so our method regularly repeat the same pattern (one point doubling and one point addition(or subtraction)) in each iteration, therefore, SPA cannot extract any information about the secret key k by observing the power consumption. The proposed method has a constant run time which ensure the resistance against timing attacks. Moreover, the proposed method dose not make use of any dummy operation, therefore, it is resistant to safe error fault attacks. In addition to that, our proposed method resistant to DPA, Okeya and Sakurai's second-order DPA, RPA, ZPA and Geiselmann-Steinwandt's attacks.

Index Terms—Scalar multiplication, Simple power analysis, Differential power analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

In elliptic curve cryptography a particular target of SCA attacks is the secret scalar k in scalar multiplication algorithm. Various countermeasures against SCA attacks have been proposed in the literature such as [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12] and [13].

More countermeasures were proposed by using recoding representation of the scalar. In [14], Möller proposed a SPA resistant window method based on 2^ω -ary window method, where each digit that is equal to zero is replaced with -2^ω , and the next most significant digit is incremented by one. Therefore, the scalar k is represented as

$$k = \sum_{i=0}^{\acute{a}-1} d_i 2^{i\omega} \text{ with } d_i \in \mathcal{B} = \{-2^\omega, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots, \pm(2^\omega - 1)\}.$$

where \acute{a} is equal to a or $a + 1$ when a is the bit length of k in original 2^ω -ary method.

In [15], Okeya and Takagi proposed a SCA resistant scalar multiplication based on width- ω NAF method. They generated a scalar sequence with fixed pattern. Their recoding representation make use of an odd digits $\mathcal{B} = \{\pm 1, \pm 3, \dots, \pm 2^\omega - 1\}$ and it assume an odd scalar. The recoding works in right to left and it consist, at step i , in incrementing d_i and replace d_{i-1} by $d_{i-1} - 2^\omega$ whenever d_i is even. Since by assumption d_0 is odd and the recoding work from the least to most significant digits, d_{i-1} is always odd and greater than zero at step i . Therefore, if at step i , d_i is even then the updated value of $d_{i-1} = d_{i-1} - 2^\omega \in \mathcal{B}$.

In [16], Sakai and Sakura proposed methods of attacks on the exponent recoding for width- ω NAF [17] and signed/unsigned fractional window representation [18].

In [19], Joye and Tunstall proposed methods of recoding exponent/scalar to allow for regular implementations of m -ary algorithm. Their proposed method make use of both signed and unsigned exponent/scalar digits.

In [20], Mtthieu proposed a signed binary algorithm using signed representation of an odd scalar k . The signed representation is obtained by converting the binary representation of the odd scalar $k = \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} k_i 2^i$ to a signed representation $k = \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} d_i 2^i$ with $d_i \in \{-1, 1\}$. The representation is based on the fact that for all $\omega > 1$, we have $1 = 2^\omega - \sum_{i=0}^{\omega-1} 2^i$. The full signed expansion of the scalar k is obtained by

$$d_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = l - 1 \text{ or } l - 2 \\ (-1)^{1+k_{i+1}} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

In [21] Lim and Lee proposed a comb method that represent the scalar k as a binary matrix of ω rows and d columns. The matrix is then processed column-wise from right-to-left or from left-to-right. The probability to have a zero column is less than to have a single zero bit, therefore, Lim and Lee [21] method offers a better resistance against SPA attacks than the binary method [22] or width- ω NAF method. However, the execution of a Simple Power Analysis (SPA) attacks on Lim and Lee [21] can allow to detect some information on the bits

of the scalar, since their method performs an addition and doubling operations for a non zero column, and only doubling for the zero column.

Many countermeasures to SPA attack on the comb method were proposed in [22], [23], [24], [25] and [26], we will discuss them in Section III.

In this paper we prove that the length of the recoding of the odd scalar k using Joye and Tunstall regular signed-digit recoding [19] with $m = 2$ is equal to the length of the binary representation of the scalar k . Then, we propose a regular SPA resistant elliptic curve scalar multiplication algorithm based on Lim and Lee [21] fixed-base comb method. Our method represents the odd scalar k in base 2 using Joye and Tunstall [19] regular signed-digit recoding. Then, the scalar k is divided into $\omega \times d$ blocks according to the method of Lim and Lee [21] and then, processes columnwise. All the columns are non-zero columns, so our method regularly repeats the same pattern (one point doubling and one point addition (or subtraction)) in each iteration, therefore, SPA cannot extract any information about the secret key k by observing the power consumption. The proposed method has a constant run time which ensures the resistance against timing attacks. Moreover the proposed method does not make use of any dummy operation, therefore, it is resistant to safe error fault attacks. In order to prevent (DPA) attacks, we further make use of randomization techniques as proposed by Coron, and to prevent our proposed method against Okeya and Sakurai's second-order DPA attack, we change the randomization of each pre-computed point after getting the point in the table as suggested by Hedabou et al. In addition to that, by using randomized linearly transformed coordinate as proposed by Itoh et al. our proposed method is resistant to RPA, ZPA and Geiselmann-Steinwandt's attacks.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In Section II we review Lim and Lee [21] fixed base comb method. In Section III we discuss the resistance of Lim and Lee [21] comb method to side channel attack, and we review methods of Hedabou et al [22], [23], Feng et al [25], [24], and Hamburg [26]. In Section IV, we review Joye and Tunstall [19] regular signed digit recoding method and prove that the length of the recoding of the odd scalar k using Joye and Tunstall [19] recoding with $m = 2$ is equal to the length of the binary representation of the scalar k . In Section V, we propose a SPA resistant elliptic curve scalar multiplication algorithm based on Lim and Lee [21] fixed base comb method. In Section VI, we convert the method proposed in Section V to a regular SPA resistant elliptic curve scalar multiplication algorithm. Finally, in Section VII we conclude our work.

II. FIXED BASE COMB METHODS

In elliptic curve cryptography, the computation $Q = kP$ where k is an integer and P is an elliptic curve point is known as scalar multiplication method and it is the most time consuming operation in elliptic curve cryptography. Many methods have been introduced in the literature [27], [28]. When the elliptic curve base point P is fixed, the efficiency of scalar

multiplication methods can be improved by pre-computations. If all $2^l P$ points are pre-computed, then the complexity of the scalar multiplication is reduced to only $\frac{l}{2}A$. The main idea of fixed base comb methods is to represent the scalar k as a binary matrix of ω rows and d columns. The matrix is then processed column-wise from right-to-left or from left-to-right. In [29] Brickell, Gordon, McCurley, and Wilson proposed a fixed-base windowing technique (BGMW), they proposed to split the scalar k into d slices, where $d = \lceil l/\omega \rceil$. The runtime complexity is then reduced to $(2^\omega + d - 3)A$.

In [21], Lim and Lee proposed an efficient fixed base comb method. We will illustrate the fixed base comb method [30] based on Lim and Lee [21] method using only one table.

A. Lim and Lee [21] Fixed Base Comb Method:

Let $(k_{l-1}, \dots, k_1, k_0)$ be the binary representation of the scalar k , and let $\omega > 1$ be a window width. The binary representation of the scalar k is represented in a binary matrix of ω rows and d columns, where $d = \lceil l/\omega \rceil$. If P is an elliptic curve point, for all $(b_{\omega-1}, \dots, b_1, b_0) \in \mathbb{Z}_2^\omega$, we define

$$[b_{\omega-1}, \dots, b_1, b_0]P = b_0P + b_12^dP + \dots + b_{\omega-1}2^{(\omega-1)d}.$$

Algorithm 1, illustrates the fixed base comb method algorithm based on Lim and Lee [21] method.

Algorithm 1 Fixed Base Comb Method [21]

Input: a positive scalar $k = (k_{l-1}, \dots, k_1, k_0)$, elliptic curve point P and a window width $\omega > 1$.

Output: kP .

- 1: $d = \lceil l/\omega \rceil$.
 - 2: Precompute $[b_{\omega-1}, \dots, b_1, b_0]P$ for all $(b_{\omega-1}, \dots, b_1, b_0) \in \mathbb{Z}_2^\omega$.
 - 3: By padding k on the left with 0's if necessary, write $k = K^{\omega-1} || \dots || K^1 || K^0$, where each K^j is a bit string of length d . Let K_i^j denote the i th bit of K^j . Define $\mathbb{K}_i \equiv [K_i^{\omega-1}, \dots, K_i^1, K_i^0]$.
 - 4: $Q = O$.
 - 5: **For** $i = d - 1$ **to** 0 **do** .
 - 6: $Q = 2Q$.
 - 7: $Q = Q + \mathbb{K}_i P$.
 - 8: **Return** Q .
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Lim and Lee [21] fixed base comb method stores $(2^\omega - 1)$ points in the pre-computation stage. The total cost in the pre-computation stage is $(\omega - 1)d$ doubling operations and $(2^\omega - \omega - 1)$ point additions. The total cost in the evaluation stage is $(d - 1)$ doubling operations and $\frac{2^\omega - 1}{2}(d - 1)$ point additions and the total cost is $(\omega d - 1)$ doubling operations and $(2^\omega - \omega - 1 + \frac{2^\omega - 1}{2}(d - 1))$ point additions [25].

In [31], Tsaur and Chou proposed a fixed base comb method by applying a NAF representation of the scalar k , and using a special doubling operation proposed by Sakai and Sakurai [32]. In [33] Mohamed et al. proposed an enhancement of Tsaur and Chou [31] method. However, Lim and Lee [21] method is more efficient than both Tsaur and Chou [31] or Mohamed et al [33] methods.

III. RESISTANCE TO SIDE CHANNEL ATTACKS

Side-Channel Analysis (SCA) attacks have been first introduced by Kocher et al. [34], [35], [36] in 1996. By monitoring physical characteristics of a given implementation, e.g., the power consumption or the timing behavior, an attacker is able to extract secret information such as the ephemeral key or private key in asymmetric-key cryptography. Two main kinds of SCA attacks are Simple Power Analysis (SPA) and Differential Power Analysis (DPA) attacks [34], [35] and [36].

The fixed base comb method of Lim and Lee [21] is *per se* not resistant to SCA. It performs an addition and doubling operations for a non zero column, and only doubling operation for the zero column. Therefore, an execution of a (SPA) attacks on the comb method [21] can allow to detect whether the column is zero or not, and hence, leak some information on the bits of the scalar. Since the leak will just determine whether the column (bit string of the scalar) not the single bit is zero or not, the comb method of Lim and Lee [21] offers a better resistance against SPA attacks than the binary method [22] or width- ω NAF method.

In [22], Hedabou et al. proposed the first SCA resistant method for fixed-base comb method based on Lim and Lee [21] method. For an odd scalar k their method constructs a new sequence of bit-string \mathbb{K}'_i representing the scalar k from its bits-string \mathbb{K}_i as introduced by Lim and Lee as follows. Let $s_0 = 1$ and construct the rest recursively as

$$\begin{cases} (\mathbb{K}'_i, s_i) = (\mathbb{K}_{i-1}, s_{i-1}) \\ (\mathbb{K}'_{i-1}, s_{i-1}) = (\mathbb{K}_{i-1}, -s_{i-1}) \end{cases}$$

if $\mathbb{K}_i = 0$ and $(\mathbb{K}'_i, s_i) = (\mathbb{K}_i, s_i)$ otherwise. All the new bit-strings are different from zero.

In [23] Hedabou et al. proposed a second SCA resistant method for fixed-base comb method based on Lim and Lee [21] method. Hedabou et al. [23] method assume and odd integer k , and modify the binary representation of k to a signed representation $k = \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} k_i 2^i$ where $k_i \in \{-1, 1\}$, by replacing every zero bit in the binary representation of k by 1 or -1, depending of its neighbour bits. The process start from the least significant bit to the most significant bit. For an odd integer k , assume that k_i is the first bit such that $k_i = 0$, replace k_i by $k_i = k_i + 1 = 1$ and $k_{i-1} = k_{i-1} - 2 = -1$. This representation is based on the fact that $1 = 1 \bar{1} \bar{1} \dots \bar{1}$. To make the new representation SPA resistant, Hedabou et al. [23] proposed to touch every bit whether it is zero or not. Also, they proposed to replace k by $k + 1$ if k is even and by $k + 2$ if k is odd, then apply the new signed representation to Lim and Lee [21] comb method. $2P$ is calculated and P or $2P$ is subtracted from the result of the comb method.

In [24] Feng et al. proposed a novel comb recoding algorithm which converts an integer to a sequence of signed odd-only comb bit-columns, then they proposed several comb methods, both SPA-nonresistant and SPA-resistant. Feng et al. [24] recoding represent every odd integer k as bit columns $\{K_i\}$ such that the least significant bit of the bit column $\{K_i\}$ is either 1 or -1 and the rest bits in the same bit column is

either 0 or has the same sign as the least significant bit in the same column.

In [25] Feng et al. proposed another comb method, which converts an integer to a sequence of signed most significant bit set nonzero comb method. As in comb method of Lim and Lee [21], in Feng et al [25] the binary representation of the scalar k is first partitioned into ω binary string K^j of d bits long for each, $0 \leq j \leq \omega$, with 0 possibly padded on left. Then the method converts each bit of the highest d bits to either 1 or -1 using the fact that $1 = 1 \bar{1} \bar{1} \dots \bar{1}$. The rest of the recoding processes each bit from the least significant bit towards the $\{(\omega - 1)d - 1\}^{th}$ bit. If the current i^{th} bit is 1 and has a sign different from that of the most significant bit in the same bit column, the current bit is set to -1 and the next higher corresponding bit is added by one. The process generates ωd bits $\{b'_i\}$ and a δ .

In [26] Hamburg et al. proposed a novel signed multi-comb algorithm. Hamburg et al. method write the scalar k in signed binary form, divide the digits into disjoint blocks, then divide the digits in each block into combs.

IV. JOYE AND TUNSTALL SINGED DIGIT RECODING

In [19], Joye and Tunstall proposed methods of recoding exponent/scalar to allow for regular implementations of m -ary algorithm. Their proposed method make use of both signed and unsigned exponent/scalar digits. Joye and Tunstall [19] recoding method takes an odd scalar k and computes its $m = 2^\omega$ radix representation $(d_{l-1}, \dots, d_1, d_0)_m$ with digits that takes odd values in $\{-(m-1), \dots, -1, 1, \dots, m-1\}$,

$$k = \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} d_i m^i \text{ with } d_i \in \mathcal{B} = \{\pm 1, \pm 3, \dots, \pm(m-1)\} \text{ and } d_i \text{ odd.}$$

Algorithm 2, illustrates Joye and Tunstall (Odd) Singed-Digit Recoding Method [19].

Algorithm 2 Joye and Tunstall (Odd) Singed-Digit Recoding Method [19]

Input: Odd positive scalar k and a positive integer $m = 2^\omega$.

Output: $k = (k_{l-1}, \dots, k_1, k_0)_{\pm m}$ with $k_i \in \{\pm 1, \pm 3, \dots, \pm(2^\omega - 1)\}$ and k_i odd.

- 1: $i = 0$.
 - 2: **While** $(k > m)$ **do**.
 - 3: $k_i = (k \bmod 2m) - m$.
 - 4: $k = (k - k_i)/m$.
 - 5: $i = i + 1$.
 - 6: $k_i = k$.
 - 7: **Return** $(k_{l-1}, \dots, k_1, k_0)_{\pm m}$.
-

THEOREM

If the binary representation of the odd scalar k , is $k = (d_{m-1}, \dots, d_1, d_0)_2$; $d_i \in \{0, 1\}$, with $d_0 = 1, d_{m-1} = 1$, then, the singed digit recoding of the odd scalar k using Joye and Tunstall singed-digit recoding algorithm with $m = 2$, will be of length m . That is $k = (k_{m-1}, \dots, k_1, k_0)_2, k_i \in \{-1, 1\}$.

Proof:

Suppose at the start of the i^{th} step, the value of the scalar k , is $k = (h_{t-1}, \dots, h_1, h_0)_2$, with $h_0 = 1, h_{t-1} = 1$. So we have:

$$k = h_{t-1} * 2^{t-1} + \dots + h_1 * 2 + h_0.$$

Now, $l = k(mod A) = h_1 * 2 + h_0$. Thus:

$$k_i = l - 2 = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } h_1 = 0 \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Accordingly, $(k - k_i)/2 = h_{t-1} * 2^{t-2} + \dots + h_2 * 2 + h'$. We have two cases to consider for the value of h' :

$$h' = \begin{cases} (h_0 - k_i)/2 = (1 - (-1))/2 = 1 & \text{if } h_1 = 0 \\ (h_1 * 2 + h_0 - k_i)/2 = (2 + 1 - 1)/2 = 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Therefore, in both cases $h' = 1$. So, at the end of the i^{th} step, the updated value of k , is $k = (h_{t-1}, \dots, h_2, h')_2$, with $(t - 1)$ bits, and preserving the property that the first and the last bits are 1s.

Table I, illustrates the iterations of Joye and Tunstall signed digit recoding algorithm with $m = 2$, for the odd scalar $k = (d_{m-1}, \dots, d_1, d_0)_2$, from which we conclude that the representation is $k = (k_{m-1}, \dots, k_1, k_0)_2, k_i \in \{-1, 1\}$ as required.

TABLE I

THE ITERATIONS OF JOYE AND TUNSTALL SIGNED DIGIT RECODING ALGORITHM WITH $m = 2$, FOR THE ODD SCALAR $k = (d_{m-1}, \dots, d_1, d_0)_2$

Step $i =$	Value of k	Output
0	$(d_{m-1}, \dots, d_1, d_0)_2$	k_0 and $k = (d_{m-1}, \dots, d_2, d'_1)_2$
1	$(d_{m-1}, \dots, d_2, d'_1)_2$	k_1 and $k = (d_{m-1}, \dots, d_3, d'_2)_2$
2	$(d_{m-1}, \dots, d_3, d'_2)_2$	k_2 and $k = (d_{m-1}, \dots, d_4, d'_3)_2$
3	$(d_{m-1}, \dots, d_4, d'_3)_2$	k_3 and $k = (d_{m-1}, \dots, d_5, d'_4)_2$
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
$m - 2$	$(d_{m-1}, d'_{m-2})_2$	k_{m-2} and $k = (d_{m-1})_2$
$m - 1$	$(d_{m-1})_2$	$k_{m-1} = d_{m-1}$.

From this theorem, we conclude that when the odd scalar k is represented using Joye and Tunstall [19] signed digit recoding algorithm with $m = 2$ (using only $\{-1, 1\}$) then the length will be one of leastest length among all signed representations of the odd integer k using only $\{-1, 1\}$.

V. SPA RESISTANT FIXED-BASE COMB METHOD

In this section, we propose a SPA resistant elliptic-curve scalar multiplication algorithm using fixed-base comb method. For this, our proposed method assume an odd scalar and represent the scalar k in a signed representation using Joye and Tunstall [19] regular signed digit recoding with $m = 2$.

$$k = \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} k_i 2^i \text{ with } k_i \in \{-1, 1\}.$$

Then, we apply the comb method of Lim and Lee [21] to partition the signed representation of the scalar k into ω

string K^j of $d = \lceil l/\omega \rceil$ bits long for each, $0 \leq j < \omega$ i.e $k = K^{\omega-1} || \dots || K^1 || K^0$. In case if l is not divisible by ω , we avoid padding with zero on the left to not destroy the regularity of the scalar recoding, we change the $(l - 1)^{th}$ bit to -1 and pad on the left with -1 except the last bit (the $d\omega - 1$ bit) we pad it with 1, using the fact that $1 = 1 \bar{1} \bar{1} \dots \bar{1}$.

Let K_i^j denote the i^{th} bit of K^j .

$$\begin{bmatrix} K^0 \\ K^1 \\ \vdots \\ K^j \\ \vdots \\ K^{\omega-1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{d-1}^0 & \dots & K_i^0 & \dots & K_0^0 \\ K_{d-1}^1 & \dots & K_i^1 & \dots & K_0^1 \\ \vdots & & \vdots & & \vdots \\ K_{d-1}^j & \dots & K_i^j & \dots & K_0^j \\ \vdots & & \vdots & & \vdots \\ K_{d-1}^{\omega-1} & \dots & K_i^{\omega-1} & \dots & K_0^{\omega-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

Define $\mathbb{K}_i \equiv [K_i^{\omega-1}, \dots, K_i^1, K_i^0]$, we guarantee that all \mathbb{K}_i are non zero column(since all the bits are non zero). Define $[b_{\omega-1}, \dots, b_1, b_0]P = b_0P + b_12^dP + \dots + b_{\omega-1}2^{(\omega-1)d}$, and compute $[b_{\omega-1}, \dots, b_1, b_0]P$ for all $(1, b_{\omega-2}, \dots, b_1, b_0)$ where $b_i \in \{-1, 1\}$ for all $0 \leq i \leq (\omega - 2)$.

Algorithm 3, illustrates our proposed SPA fixed base comb method. If the most significant bit of \mathbb{K}_i is -1, then the point addition in the for loop will execute point subtraction and we will implement it in a regular way in the next section.

Algorithm 3 Proposed SPA Fixed Base Comb Method

Input: an odd positive scalar $k = (k_{l-1}, \dots, k_1, k_0)_2$, elliptic curve point P .

Output: kP .

- 1: $d = \lceil l/\omega \rceil$.
- 2: Represent the odd scalar k in a signed representation, using Joye and Tunstall [19] recoding method in Algorithm 2 with $m = 2$.
- 3: Precompute $[1, b_{\omega-2}, \dots, b_1, b_0]P$ for all $b_i \in \{-1, 1\}$, $\forall 0 \leq i \leq (\omega - 2)$.
- 4: By padding k on the left (change the $(l - 1)^{th}$ bit to -1 and pad on the left with -1 except the last bit, pad it with 1, using the fact that $1 = 1 \bar{1} \bar{1} \dots \bar{1}$) if necessary, write $k = K^{\omega-1} || \dots || K^1 || K^0$, where each K^j is a bit string of length d . Let K_i^j denote the i^{th} bit of K^j . Define $\mathbb{K}_i \equiv [K_i^{\omega-1}, \dots, K_i^1, K_i^0]$
- 5: $Q = \mathbb{K}_{d-1}P$.
- 6: **For** $i = d - 2$ **to** 0 **do** .
- 7: $Q = 2Q$.
- 8: $Q = Q + \mathbb{K}_iP$.
- 9: **Return** Q .

Algorithm 3, needs to store $2^{\omega-1}$ points in the precomputation. The total cost in the evaluation stage is $(d - 1)$ doubling operations and $(d - 1)$ point additions. However, this cost is the same in the evaluation stage(the for loop) compared to methods of Hedabou et.al [22], [23], Feng et. al [25], [24], and Hamburg [26], since all of them performs one point addition and one point doubling in each iteration.

VI. REGULAR SPA-RESISTANT FIXED-BASE COMB METHOD

Our proposed SPA fixed base comb method in the previous section is constrained for odd positive scalars. In [22], Hedabou et al. proposed to replace $k = k + 1$ if k is even, and $k = k + 2$ if k is odd. We proposed to replace $k = k - 1$ if k is even, and $k = k - 2$ if k is odd to avoid the growth of the length of $k + 2$ by one bit, and we add P or $2P$ at the end of the algorithm. Since the scalar k used in cyptography is a BigInteger, we grantee that $k-1$ and $k-2$ are still BigIntegers. If the scalar $k = (k_{l-1}, \dots, k_1, k_0)_2$ is odd, and all its bits are one's, then the length of the updated value $k = k - 2$ will be of length $(l - 1)$. In this case if $(l - 1)$ divide ω , then the value $d = (l - 1)/\omega$ will be less than the value d used in methods of Hedabou et.al [22], [23], Feng et. al [25], [24], and Hamburg [26] by one, which implies that the cost of our proposed regular method is less than all of the previous methods by one point doubling.

Also, in Algorithm 3 in line 8, if the most significant bit of \mathbb{K}_i is -1, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{K}_i P &\equiv [K_i^{\omega-1}, \dots, K_i^1, K_i^0]P \\ &\equiv [-1, K_i^{\omega-2}, \dots, K_i^1, K_i^0]P \\ &\equiv [-1, -K_i^{\omega-2}, \dots, -K_i^1, -K_i^0]P\end{aligned}$$

so, we multiply all the bits by -1 and recall $[1, \dots, -K_i^1, -K_i^0]P$ from the precomputation (because in the precomputation we only precomputed when the most significant bit is 1) and the point addition in the for loop will execute point subtraction. To do this in a regular way, we will apply in away similar to the method proposed by Matthieu in [20]

$$\begin{aligned}si &= \text{sign}(K_i^{\omega-1}) \\ Q &= Q + (-1)^{si} [1, (-1)^{si} k_i^{\omega-2}, \dots, (-1)^{si} K_i^1, (-1)^{si} K_i^0]P\end{aligned}$$

where $\text{sign}(x) = 1$ if $x < 0$ and 0 otherwise.

The proposed method has a constant run time which ensure the resistance against timing attacks. Moreover, the proposed method dose not make use of any dummy operation, therefore, it is resistant to safe error fault attacks

In order to prevent DPA attacks, we further make use of randomization techniques as proposed by Coron [1]. To prevent our proposed method against Okeya and Sakurai's second-order DPA attack [37], we change the randomization of each pre-computed point after getting the point in the table as suggested by Hedabou et al. [22]. Moreover, by using randomized linearly transformed coordinate as proposed by Itoh et al. [38], our proposed method is resistance to RPA, ZPA and Geiselmann-Steinwandt's attacks.

Algorithm 4, illustrates a regular version of our proposed regular SPA fixed base comb method that can be used to compute kP for any positive integer k .

Algorithm 4 Proposed Regular SPA Fixed Base Comb Method

Input: a positive scalar k , and elliptic curve point P .

Output: kP .

- 1: $r = k \pmod{2}$.
- 2: $k = k - 2^r$, $k = (k_{l-1}, \dots, k_1, k_0)_2$
- 3: $d = \lceil l/\omega \rceil$.
- 4: Represent the odd scalar k in a signed representation, using Joye and Tunstall [19] recoding method in Algorithm 2 with $m = 2$.
- 5: Precompute $[1, b_{\omega-2}, \dots, b_1, b_0]P$ for all $b_i \in \{-1, 1\}$, $\forall 0 \leq i \leq (\omega - 2)$.
- 6: By padding k on the left (change the $(l - 1)^{th}$ bit to -1 and pad on the left with -1 except the last bit, pad it with 1, using the fact that $1 = 1 \bar{1} \bar{1} \dots \bar{1}$.) if necessary, write $k = K^{\omega-1} || \dots || K^1 || K^0$, where each K^j is a bit string of length d . Let K_i^j denote the i th bit of K^j . Define $\mathbb{K}_i \equiv [K_i^{\omega-1}, \dots, K_i^1, K_i^0]$
- 7: $Q = \mathbb{K}_{d-1} P$.
- 8: **For** $i = d - 2$ **to** 0 **do** .
- 9: $Q = 2Q$.
- 10: $si = \text{sign}(K_i^{\omega-1})$ (where $\text{sign}(x) = 1$ if $x < 0$ and 0 otherwise.)
- 11: $Q = Q + (-1)^{si} [1, (-1)^{si} k_i^{\omega-2}, \dots, (-1)^{si} K_i^1, (-1)^{si} K_i^0]P$.
- 12: $Q = Q + 2^r P$
- 13: **Return** Q .

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proved that the length of the recoding of the odd scalar k using Joye and Tunstall regular signed-digit recoding with $m = 2$ is equal to the length of the binary representation of the scalar k . Then, we proposed a regular SPA resistant elliptic curve scalar multiplication algorithm based on Lim and Lee [21] fixed base comb method. Our proposed method is resistant against SPA, timing, and safe-error fault, DPA and second-order DPA attacks. In addition to that, by using randomized linearly transformed coordinate our proposed method is resistant to RPA, ZPA and Geiselmann-Steinwandt's attacks.

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